

On the geometrical structure of quantised space

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Space itself is quantised and its properties are responsible for the creation of phenomenological reality. The latter means that our sensory reality is a construct of mutual relations that originates from the dynamics of quantised space. A brief description.

Introduction

The volume of the universe shows to be quantised.^[1] Now the question is how to determine the mathematical properties of the units of the quantised volume. Because figure 1 is just a schematic image of a static volume that is build up by identical small volumes with the same shape as the big enveloping volume.

figure 1

The properties of phenomenological reality are investigated and described in physics. Unfortunately the description of these properties in theoretical physics are not well suited to understand how the quantisation of the volume of the universe creates reality like we know it. Although it is reasonable to assume that there must be a direct relation between the mathematical properties of the basic quantum fields (QFT) and the properties of the structure of quantised space.

It is also reasonable to assume that the properties of the structure of quantised space are not only determined by the dynamics of the individual unit, but also by the dynamics of all the units together. Because every unit of quantised space shares its boundary with adjacent units. It shows that without the right insight into the configuration of the structure it is hard to determine the other properties.

References:

1. S.E Grimm (2024); “The box without walls”
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The static structure

In the schematic image of figure 1 every unit (cube) shares its boundary with 6 adjacent units. So every plane of the unit/cube is a joint plane. So far, so good. But if every unit has 8 adjacent units, or even 13, it is clear that without the correct configuration every attempt to determine the properties of quantised space is like guessing. And the literature of QFT or even Einstein’s spacetime isn’t helpful either.

The idea that the volume of the universe is quantised, doesn’t originate from modern physics. It was the ancient Greek philosopher and mathematician [Parmenides of Elea](#) and his student [Zeno of Elea](#) who wrote about the concept. Unfortunately their original writings are lost so our knowledge about the concept comes from the writings of other ancient Greek philosophers. Fortunately [Zeno’s paradox](#) of Achilles and the tortoise shows that their concept of an underlying reality that creates phenomenological reality had a metric. Showing that infinite divisibility is not part of the concept of an underlying creating reality/structure.

The units of the quantised volume of the universe^[1] must also generate all the dynamics – actually *transformations* under invariant volume – in the universe. The consequence is that the volume and the shape of every unit is the result of an internal “shape-forming” mechanism. Of course in cooperation with the same mechanism of the other units.

The image in figure 1 doesn’t show any dynamics and it is also difficult to hypothesise some kind of internal dynamical mechanism. Moreover, a cube is not a common shape, it is more a construct. The only geometrical shape that exists everywhere and at every scale size too, is the shape of the sphere. And it is also the only true geometrical scalar.

In the image below – figure 2 – I have drawn 2 possible configurations of spheres, a cubic and a triangle arrangement. If I push slowly together the spheres of each arrangement the spheres are forced to deform their shape. But it is clear that there is less force needed to fill the empty space in between the blue spheres with their deformed volume – maybe just 3 concentric shells – than the amount of force needed to deform the orange spheres to get the same result. Because the gap of empty space in between the orange spheres is much larger.

All the spheres in figure 2 are drawn with concentric shells because that is the way to calculate the increasing resistance of a sphere against deformation. The relation is determined by the mutual difference in surface area of each shell. Figure 3 shows the graph.

figure 2

The red line represents the radius and its corresponding resistance against deforming of a unit that is part of quantised space. In other words, the undistorted part of a unit. The resistance against deformation originates from the internal shape-forming mechanism of each unit. The blue line is the radius and related resistance against deforming of an imaginary undistorted unit (100% sphere). Although the graph seems a bit trivial, later the graph is needed to understand the average amount of surface area of the units of quantised space.

figure 3

figure 4

We can fill the volume of the universe with units in different arrangements (figure 2). But daily reality shows that the motion of a phenomenon in vacuum space does not depend on the direction of the motion. That means that the configuration of the structure of quantised space is symmetrical or nearly symmetrical.

Figure 4 shows a sphere packing that is known in mathematics as the [Kepler conjecture](#). It is a combined cubic and triangle packing (lattice) with the highest density of equal spheres in relation to the volume. Each sphere is surrounded by 12 adjacent spheres. So it is possible to construct the shape of an imaginary symmetrical unit.

figure 5

The image in figure 5 shows an imaginary unit of quantised space with the shape of a rhombic dodecahedron. Inside the transparent boundary is the undistorted sphere (in geometry the inscribed sphere of the dodecahedron). The light blue volume around the sphere is the distorted part of the unit. Figure 4 shows that every undistorted sphere has 12 points of contact with the adjacent spheres. In figure 5 the black arrows inside the sphere point to the centre of each rhombus. These are the points of contact with the undistorted spheres of the 12 adjacent units (see figure 6). The percentage of the volume of the sphere and the distorted volume in relation to the unit is about 74% and 26%.

figure 6

Topological deformation

The graph in figure 3 shows the resistance against deformation of the internal *scalar mechanism* (= spherical-shape forming mechanism). The radii of the spheres inside the lattice in figure 4 are set to $r = 1,0$. The consequence is that the deformed part of the unit ($r = 1,105 \rightarrow r = 1,0$) has lost its spherical shape based resistance against deformation.

Figure 7 shows the various aspects of the internal configuration of the unit of quantised space. Image I shows the distorted volume (E) and the undistorted part (S). Image II shows that the points of contact of the undistorted part (S) with the adjacent spheres create 1-dimensional vectors inside the sphere (= scalar). Because the undistorted part cannot increase its radius because of the identical scalar mechanism of the adjacent units.

figure 7

Image III (cross section) shows that the configuration of the scalar mechanism of the deformed part of the unit (E) is not completely distorted. Actually, it is around the points of contact with the other scalars around that the hypothetical configuration of concentric shells is interrupted.

Figure 8 shows the consequences in relation to the capacity of the scalar mechanism to retain some of its distorted internal spherical configuration. It is obvious that both units first have to restore the spherical shape of the scalars in their point of contact before they can influence each other in point A or even point B.

figure 8

The geometrical relations between the surface area and the volumes of the scalar and the deformed part of the unit are determined by the irrational numbers $\sqrt{2}$ and π . It shows that there doesn't exist some kind of a geometrical equilibrium between the scalar and the deformed part of the unit. The consequence is that the internal scalar mechanism of every unit is out of balance. It will result in a continuous rearrangement of the shape of each unit of the structure.

figure 9

The volume of each unit of quantised space is invariant.^[1] That means that every change of the shape of a unit is a 3D [topological deformation](#) under invariant volume. Figure 9 (cross section) shows the principle.

The 2 rectangle bodies I and II have an identical invariant volume and a joint plane. If the amount of surface area of the joint plane increases, each body has to transfer parts of its volume – actually a flux of “infinite” small grains of volume – within its boundary. But this is only possible if both bodies transfer the own flux of volume synchronously with the transferred flux of volume of the other body. In other words, in the direction of the 2 blue arrows or in the direction of the 2 green arrows.

The consequence is that the amount of topological deformation – the transfer of parts of the internal volume – is equal for the 2 bodies. Therefore, if the shape of the deformation is equal for both bodies, h_a will be equal to h_b (see figure 9). The image in figure 10 shows that the smallest amount of topological deformation – the quantum of energy (the Planck constant) – is not generated by only one

unit. Because every topological deformation is the result of a dual change: the creation of a local surplus of deformation synchronously with the creation of a local deficit of deformation (the complementary transfer of internal volume by the 2 adjacent bodies).

figure 10

The image of an imaginary unit with 12 planes in figure 5 shows that even the smallest amount of topological deformation – the surplus and its complementary deficit of topological deformation – can involve all the 12 joint planes of the unit and adjacent units. So is it reasonable to expect that one joint plane can deform in 2 directions like the joint plane in figure 9 and 10?

Topological generated vectors

Figure 11 shows the deformation of a joint plane between 2 units. The dark blue colour indicates the volume of the deformed part of both units that is involved in the transfer of some volume by both units.

figure 11

The image shows the deformation of the joint plane but not the mechanism that facilitated the deformation. Although it is obvious that the “power” of the deformation is the internal scalar mechanism of the units in relation to all the other units around.

Far smaller deformations of the joint plane between 2 units – in relation to the deformation in figure 11 – have still the same shape. Figure 12 shows enlarged spheres in relation to figure 11 but the shape of the deformation is the same.

figure 12

The faces of the right and left unit are drawn too to accentuate the bare part of the scalar of the unit at the left. The consequence is that in and around the point of contact between the scalars of both units there is an unbalance in the mutual “pressure” in the joint plane. Although the unbalance can only be mediated to other units by the point of contact at the opposite plane of the left unit. The cross section in figure 13 shows the situation and the amount of deformation is equal to the deformation in figure 11 (different point of view).

figure 13

I have drawn the vectors (see figure 5) and the pressure of the transferred volume to the joint plane by unit A. If unit A is symmetrical – like figure 5 – the 12 vectors inside the scalar have the same magnitude. Figure 14 shows the bare vectors of figure A. However, the pressure of the deformed volume of unit A will increase the magnitude of its vector in the point of contact with unit B. The consequence is that

figure 14

unit B cannot push back the increased topological deformation of unit A in the joint plane if there isn't any help by an opposite vector from other units.

The vectors in figure 14 represent the resistance against deformation of the scalar of a unit in the diagram of figure 3 ($r = 1.0$). In other words, the amount of topological deformation of the shape of the units in every plane of their boundary will be super positioned on the vectors of their scalars. That means super positioned on the vectors of the undistorted scalar mechanism in relation to the push of the other equal scalars around in the 12 points of contact. It is obvious that the situation radically changes if a scalar is forced to decrease its radius ($r < 1.0$).

Conservation of transformations

Figure 9 shows the principle of 3D topological deformation under invariant volume. The principle suggests that it is possible to increase or decrease the amount of surface area of the joint plane. But the image also shows that the increase and decrease of surface area means that internal volume is transformed into surface area and surface area is transformed into volume.

The transformation of the shape of a unit under invariant volume means that the total transfer by the flux of infinite small grains of volume inside the unit is conserved. A unit has 12 planes so I can express the shape of a unit with the help of the volume increase/decrease (Δ) in every plane:

$$\sum \Delta V_1 + \Delta V_2 + \Delta V_3 + \dots + \Delta V_{12} = 0$$

The internal scalar mechanism of every unit tries to expand the radius of its undistorted volume, the scalar. In practise it means that the unit tries to minimise the differences between the flux of volume in relation to the increase/decrease of the volume in the 12 planes. But every change of volume in a joint plane means an opposite change in the joint plane of the adjacent unit. In other words, we have to conclude that all the changes of the shape of the units of quantised space are conserved. Unfortunately, there is a problem.

Suppose that the universe is tessellated with identical rhombic dodecahedra (figure 5). Now the total joint surface area of all the units together is symmetrical and fixed. The "power" to change the shape of a unit is the internal scalar mechanism. But there must be an opportunity – a local unbalance – for the unit to change its volume. These opportunities don't exist in a flat universe.

The consequence is that the total amount of topological deformation of all the units of quantised space exceeds the minimal surface area of a universe tessellated with identical rhombic dodecahedra. It raises the question why.

Figure 2 shows the cubic and triangle arrangements of imaginary units before they get deformed to tessellate the volume of the universe. To fill all the volume of the universe the units with a triangle arrangement have to deform less concentric shells (undistorted scalar mechanism) in relation to units with a cubic arrangement.

Figure 3 shows the resistance against deformation of the scalar mechanism of a unit. Radius $r = 1,0$ represents the undistorted scalar in vacuum space (no decreased scalars). But there is no clear relation with the size of the boundary of a deformed unit in quantised space. Nevertheless it is reasonable to suppose that the unbalance between scalar layers with a cubic and triangle arrangement is responsible for the surplus of topological deformation in the universe. See figure 4.

figure 15

Not at least because the difference between both scalar packings shows the ratio $1,414.213 r : 1,632.993 r$.^[2] If we imagine a large sphere – no matter its radius – the boundary of the imaginary sphere reflects the difference in density of both scalar packings. Actually the density of the units of discrete space in relation to quantised space as the rest frame of the universe. Figure 15 shows the distribution of the variances at the boundary of the sphere; see for details reference 2.

References:

2. S.E. Grimm (2021); "Discrete space and the scalar lattice (3.0)"
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5771124
<https://zenodo.org/record/5771124>

Synchronised deformation

The invariant and equal volume of every unit of quantised space has consequences. Because one unit cannot change its shape without the synchronous change of the shape of all the other units of quantised space in the universe. Every unit has identical basic properties, reflected by the existence of the Planck constant (h) and the constant speed of light (c). Both universal constants are manifestations of the universal electric field in vacuum space.

The synchronisation of all the topological changes of the universal electric field can be interpreted as the constant of quantum time (t_q). Because in between the start and the end of the transfer of a flux of volume within the boundary of a unit there is no change in direction of the transfer of volume inside the unit. The consequence is that the Planck constant (h) and the constant of quantum time (t_q) are a duality if we interpret energy and time as different concepts.

Conclusion

The volume of the universe has a structure because all the phenomena are directly related to 2 properties: volume and change. So it is not reasonable to suppose that space is really homogenous.

The dynamic geometrical structure of quantised space creates a reality of mutual relations between the units of quantised space. The reality of mutual relations is the subject of physics research. Observing, measuring and interpreting the mutual relations with the help of the [scientific method](#).